

treatment, and water depth class.

In control fields, sedges, broad-leaved weeds, and grasses were markedly reduced as water level increased (see table). Fish modified this general pattern by reducing sedges and broad-leaved weeds at low water depth (about 5 cm) when compared with the control. In contrast, fish enhanced weed growth at higher water depths. Similar results were obtained for *Marsilea crenata* and the percentage of area covered by non-algae

weeds. Results for grasses and *Monochoria vaginalis* are less conclusive, but show the same trend. Algae were reduced at 2, 6, 10, and 14 cm of water.

At 3 cm, the average number of uprooted sedges and broad-leaved weeds was 7.3/m² in rice - fish fields compared with 0.5/m² in controls; at 5 cm, it was 2.6/m² for rice - fish fields compared with 0.3/m² in controls. The results indicate that fish prefer shallow areas in ricefields

as a feeding place, possibly because food is more abundant there.

Fish affect ricefields in two major ways: their feeding activities reduce weed growth, and the accelerated turnover of organic matter enhances weed development. These feeding and fertilizing effects counteract each other. Water regime markedly influences the degree to which each effect operates. ■

Farming systems

Rice - wheat yields as affected by tillage and planting date

N. R. Das, N. N. Mukherjee, and S. Sen, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, West Bengal, India

We studied wheat yield productivity after the main crop of transplanted wet season (TWS) rice in West Bengal. Wheat was planted under irrigated conditions using different planting dates and numbers of tillages at the Agricultural University Farm during 1988-89 and 1989-90.

The rice - wheat rotation was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications, with tillage in main plots and planting date in 7.5 × 2.5-m subplots. Soil is medium fertile with pH 6.8, 0.061% total N, 7.4 kg available P/ha, and 141 kg available K/ha.

After the harvest of TWS IR36 rice, which yielded an average of 4.1 t grain/ha, fields were fertilized with 100-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha at the end of Oct. UP262 wheat was sown at 100 kg seed/ha in lines spaced at 25 cm on 1 Nov, 16 Nov, 1 Dec, and 16 Dec. Three tillage levels were used: zero - without plowing, but furrows for planting seed were made with hand tine; minimal - two plowings; and conventional - four plowings by bullock. Fertilizer was broadcast at sowing: 100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 41.5 kg K/ha from urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash, respectively. The wheat crops were harvested during the 1st, 2d, and 3d wk of Mar for 1st, 2d, and 3d and 4th planting dates, respectively.

The maximum grain yield of wheat was obtained from the 16 Nov planting and the

least from the 16 Dec planting. Wheat straw yields followed a similar trend (see figure).

Both wheat grain and straw yield increased with increased tillages, though yields under minimal tillage did not vary much compared with those under conventional tillage (see figure). Mid-Nov planting with either minimal or conventional tillage gave the maximum

wheat grain and straw yields after TWS rice (see figure). ■

Grain and straw yield of wheat as affected by planting date and number of tillages after transplanted wet rice. West Bengal, India, 1988-89, 1989-90 winter.

